

The Effect of Video Games on Cognitive Functions among Students at Princess Nourah University in Saudi Arabia: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Video games are widely popular, especially among youth, and their effect on cognitive functions can be both positive and negative. While excessive gaming may impair certain abilities, studies show improvements in attention, memory, perception, and coordination. With Saudi Arabia's growing interest in the gaming industry, understanding these cognitive effects is important. **Objectives:** To explore the effect of video games on some cognitive functions among students at an academic institution in Saudi Arabia. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted using convenience sampling. Data were collected through a questionnaire and the General Cognitive Assessment Battery (GCAB) via the CogniFit app. Statistical tests included t-tests, ANOVA, chi-square, and multiple regression to compare cognitive scores based on gaming habits and other factors. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. **Results:** among 389 students, 57.8% were gamers. Players showed significantly higher cognitive scores than nonplayers, especially in attention, coordination, reasoning, and perception ($p < 0.01$), with no significant difference in memory. Duration of gameplay, measured by years or time spent daily was not significantly associated with cognitive score. Most participants believed gaming benefits cognitive skills regardless of actual performance. Regression analysis showed that both gaming status and college type significantly predicted cognitive outcomes. **Conclusion:** Video game playing was significantly associated with better cognitive performance in several areas. However, time spent playing did not have a significant influence on cognitive function outcomes. While academic background influenced cognitive outcomes, these findings suggest potential cognitive benefits of gaming.

Keywords: *Video Games, multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA), Cognitive Functions.*

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Introduction

Video games have become popular leisure activities worldwide, especially among adolescents and young adults, with increased time spent playing video games of multiple game genres with different characteristics and levels of involvement required. Excessive gaming can cause impairment of

cognitive functions such as impulse control. Studies have demonstrated that video games can improve different cognitive skills such as reasoning, memory, attention, perception, and coordination. It is essential to move beyond focusing on the negatives toward understanding the positive effects, especially considering Saudi Arabia's increasing interest in developing video games. So, this study aims to explore the relationship between video games and some cognitive functions.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Duration

A cross-sectional study explored the effect of MOBA on some cognitive functions among students at PNU in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, from the first of September 2024 until April 2025.

Study Area and Setting

The study was conducted at Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University and targeted enrolled students. Participants first completed a questionnaire, followed by the GCAB assessment

Study Population

female students aged from 18 to 25 years, selected from different colleges within the university

Sample Frame

The sampling frame consisted of all students enrolled at the academic institution during the academic year 2024–2025.

Sample Size

The sample size for this study was calculated using the free Online collector for public,

$$\text{Sample size equation used } n = \frac{[DEFF * Np(1-p)]}{[(d2/Z_{1-\alpha/2} * (N-1) + p * (1-p)]} \quad (1)$$

Population size (N):36901 and Various Confidence Levels 95%The sample size was calculated to be 381.

collected 389 samples, more than the required sample to avoid participants deleting their accounts, or the participants' accounts not associated with us.

Sample Selection

A convenience sampling technique was used to select participants who were available and willing to participate.

Data Collection Tools

Data collection was conducted using a structured questionnaire featuring fixed-response items, including multiple-choice questions and closed-ended questions divided into two sections: the first focused on participant demographics, while the second assessed their gaming patterns. Selected students who provided informed consent were invited to complete a self-administered questionnaire.

Then, The General Cognitive Assessment Battery (GCAB) by CogniFit was used to assess five cognitive functions: reasoning, memory, attention, coordination, and perception. Developed by psychologists, this validated tool is designed to accurately evaluate a broad spectrum of cognitive abilities. It consists of a comprehensive set of cognitive tasks, presented as engaging brain games,

aimed at measuring and enhancing cognitive function. The procedures were conducted in two formats: online and on-site at the university, with researcher supervision to minimize misunderstandings. Additionally, GCAB includes a variety of tasks. To maintain consistency, all participants completed the GCAB in a predetermined sequence.

Before initiating the procedures, all aspects were thoroughly explained to the participants, and informed consent was obtained from each of them. Upon completing the GCAB, participants received a notification via the CogniFit application after entering their email, granting us access to their cognitive function data, which remained restricted until they provided explicit consent. This measure is part of the privacy and confidentiality protocols upheld by the application

Cognitive Assessment Battery (CAB)®

The neuropsychological Cognitive Assessment Battery (CAB) is a clinically validated, reimbursable, and reliable tool designed for both professional settings, such as clinics, schools, and research institutions, and personal use by individuals or families. It is used in over 2,700 Neurology, Primary Care, and Geriatrics practices worldwide.

The General Cognitive Assessment Battery (GCAB) is an online neuropsychological assessment that lasts approximately 30 to 40 minutes and is suitable for both children aged 7 and above and adults. The assessment consists of 17 levels, evaluating 22 cognitive functions across five domains: attention, memory, coordination, perception, and reasoning. Before beginning, participants receive both written and video instructions to ensure clarity and understanding.

Once players understand the gameplay, they proceed to a practice session. After confirming their understanding, a prompt appears asking, "Do you want to start or repeat the practice?" If the player selects "Start," the game begins assessing their skills. The assessment incorporates a Validity Index to ensure accurate measurement.

During the evaluation tasks, if a participant responds inattentively or appears disengaged, the system detects this and prompts them to focus more on the activities. If they adjust their behaviour, the recorded variables remain valid. However, if they do not, the affected measurements are deemed invalid and reflected in the corresponding section of the report. This report, detailing the participants' gameplay and cognitive skills is accessible upon completion. Participants whose responses remain invalid are excluded from the study.

Upon completing the GCAB, researchers will have access to both the overall cognitive score and individual scores for specific cognitive skills, including attention, memory, coordination, perception, and reasoning. These scores are presented on a scale from 0 to 100. A scores are divided into four ranges, below average (0–25,) and low within average (25–50) represent areas where cognitive abilities are weaker or have room for improvement, while high within average (50–75) and above average (75–100) represent areas where cognitive abilities are strong or above average for people of the same age and gender. (CogniFit, Inc., 2023b)

Statistical Analysis and Data Management

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic characteristics, while inferential tests were applied to examine relationships between video game use and cognitive function. Independent t-tests compared cognitive scores between players and non-players. One-way ANOVA assessed differences based on years of gaming experience. Chi-square tests explored associations between cognitive scores and both gameplay frequency and perceived impact of gaming. Multiple linear regression was used to evaluate the influence of college type and gaming status on total cognitive performance. All analyses were conducted using JMP.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Survey Participants (n=389)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Freq</i>	<i>percent</i>
Age, year		
18-19	136	35.0
20-21	203	52.2
22-23	45	11.6
24-25	5	1.9
College		
Science	60	18.5
Health	257	66.1
Humanities	72	15.4
Job alongside studying		
No	374	96.1
Part-time	10	2.6
Full-time	5	1.3
Marital status		
Single	380	97.7
Married	9	2.3
Have children		
No	386	99.2
Yes	3	0.8

Most participants were between 18 and 21 years old, with the most common age being 20–21 years (52.2%). Most participants were from health colleges (66.07%), followed by humanities (18.51%) and scientific colleges (15.42%). Nearly all participants (96.14%) were not working while studying, and a small proportion reported having part-time (2.57%) or full-time jobs (1.29%). The sample was predominantly single (97.69%) and did not have children (99.23%).

Figure 1. Prevalence of Players and Non-Players Among Students at Princess Nourah University (PNU)

A Total of 389 participants, 225 students (57.8%), reported that they play video games, while 164 students (42.2%) reported that they do not. suggesting a high prevalence of gaming behavior in this population.

Table 2. Differences in Cognitive Function Scores between Video Game Players and Non-Video Game Players (n=389)

Cognitive Function	Mean Difference (Players - Non-players)	T Ratio	df	p-value
Total Cognitive Score	5.85 (52.4 - 46.5)	3.48	329.63	0.0006
Attention	7.73 (60.1- 52.4)	4.11	350.57	< 0.0001
Coordination	8.44 (62.9 - 54.4)	4.18	317.99	< 0.0001
Reasoning	6.80 (59.1 - 52.2)	3.40	324.10	0.0008
Perception	6.23 (48.3 - 42.1)	3.65	339.38	0.0003
Memory	3.00 (46.3- 43.3)	1.38	335.15	0.1692

An independent samples t-test conducted to investigate whether engagement in video games, such as PUBG, COD Mobile, and Tekken8, is associated with differences in cognitive function scores among students at Princess Nourah University. The results showed that participants who reported playing video games (n = 225, Mean = 52.4) had significantly higher total cognitive scores compared to non-players (n = 164, Mean = 46.5), with a mean difference of 5.85 ($t(329.63) = 3.48, p = 0.0006$). Further analysis revealed significant group differences across several cognitive domains. Players demonstrated higher scores, with a mean difference of 7.73 ($t(350.57) = 4.11, p < 0.0001$, Mean Players = 60.1, Mean non-players = 52.4), as well as coordination abilities, indicated by a mean difference of 8.44 ($t(317.99) = 4.18, p < 0.0001$, Mean Players = 62.9, Mean non-players = 54.4). In terms of reasoning, players scored higher than non-players by 6.80 ($t(324.10) = 3.40, p = 0.0008$, Mean Players = 59.1, Mean non-players = 52.2), and similarly scored higher in perception and information processing, with a mean difference of 6.23 ($t(339.38) = 3.65, p = 0.0003$, Mean Players = 48.3, Mean non-players = 42.1). However, there was no statistically significant difference observed in the memory between players and non-players ($t(335.15) = 1.38, p = 0.1692$, Mean Players = 46.3, Mean non-players = 43.3), suggesting that memory-related performance may not be strongly influenced by playing video games. Overall, these findings indicate a positive association between playing video games and enhanced cognitive performance, particularly in attention, coordination, perception, and reasoning.

Table 3. ANOVA Result for Cognitive Function Scores Based on Years of Gaming Experience (n=389)

Level	n	Mean	Std Error	95% (Lower-Upper)	F	P-value
>than year	22	49.3182	3.2625	55.748 – 42.889	1.9100	0.1288
1-2 years	23	48.4348	3.1908	54.723 – 42.146		
3-4years	45	56.5333	2.2812	61.029 – 52.038		
5years and >	135	52.2593	1.3170	54.855 – 49.664		

The results of the One-Way ANOVA suggest that there is no statistically significant difference in the cognitive scores across the groups based on the number of years participants have been playing video games ($F(3, 221) = 1.91, p = 0.1288$). This shows that the number of years spent playing video games does not have a significant effect on the cognitive scores of participants.

Table 4. Total Cognitive Scores Across Daily Video Game Play Time (n=389)

Daily playing hours	n (per group)	Mean	Chi-Square	df	p-value
<1hour	50	99.06	3.97	4	0.141
1-2hours	81	112.3			

3-4hours	59	120.8		
5-6hours	30	123.4		
8 and >	5	107.4		

These results suggest that the amount of time spent playing video games, daily, was not significantly associated with variations in overall cognitive performance among the participants.

Table 5. Cognitive Score and Perception of the Positive Impact of Video Games on Cognitive Functions (n=389)

Count Total % Col % Row %	No impact	Perception of the Positive Impact	Total	Prob>ChiSq
Low	24 10.67 43.64 24.49	74 32.89 43.53 75.51	98 43.56	0.9889
High	31 13.78 56.36 24.41	96 42.67 56.47 75.59	127 56.44	
Total	55 24.44	170 75.56	225	

The contingency analysis evaluates the association between total cognitive score (Low: 0–50; High: 50–100) and participants’ perception of the positive effect of video games on cognitive functions. The Chi-square test results showed no statistically significant association between the two variables (Pearson Chi-square $p = 0.9889$). Approximately 75% of participants in both the Low and High groups reported that video games positively influence cognitive functions. These findings suggest that perceptions regarding the cognitive benefits of video games are similar across different cognitive performance levels, and no significant relationship was detected in this sample.

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Results for the Effects of College Type and Playing Combat Video Games on the Total Score of Cognitive Functions

Predictors	Unstandardized Coefficients		t-value	p-value	Adjusted R-square	F Ratio
	Beta (β)	SE				
intercept	48.042016	1.000464	48.02	0.0001*	0.071748	10.99
Do you play (No)	-3.111206	0.82228	-3.78	0.0002*		
College (Humanities)	-6.04204	1.14487	-4.17	0.0001*		
College (Health)	3.2100331	1.1436	2.81	0.0053*		

A multiple linear regression was computed predicting the total score of cognitive functions based on college type and playing combat video games (as shown in Table 6). The regression equation was significant ($F = 10.9966$, $p < 0.0001$), with an adjusted R-square of 0.0717. Both college type and playing combat video games were significant predictors of the total cognitive function score. Not playing video games was associated with a lower cognitive score ($p = 0.0002$), and students

from humanities colleges scored significantly lower than those from scientific colleges ($p < 0.0001$), while students from health colleges scored significantly higher ($p = 0.0053$).

Discussion

With the increasing popularity of video games, the number of video game players has increased worldwide. Consequently, there has been growing interest in understanding how gaming affects cognitive functions such as attention and memory. The current study aimed to explore the effect of video games on certain cognitive functions among students at Princess Nourah University. Regarding Table 1, which presents the demographic information of the participants, most students were between 18 and 21 years old, with the majority being 20 years old (29.56%). Most participants were from health colleges (66.07%) and most of them (96.14%) were not working while studying, and a small proportion reported part-time (2.57%) or full-time jobs (1.29%). These characteristics indicated that the sample consisted of young full-time students without external work commitments.

As shown in Figure 1, the findings related to the current study objective showed (57.8%) of the students reported that they play video games, while (42.2%) of the students reported that they do not play video games. This suggested a relatively high prevalence of gaming behavior among the participants. These results were consistent with the study conducted by Arafat in 2023, who investigated the relationship between video game use and cognitive functions among Adolescents. The study was conducted on 300 girls in ' schools in the Qassim region, The study found that 75% of the sample reported playing video games. He explained that the spread of internet connectivity has facilitated video gaming, enabling individuals to play with friends across different countries (Arfat, 2023).

A statistically significant association between playing video games and the improvement of some cognitive functions is shown in Table 2. Students who played video games scored higher on overall cognitive assessments compared to non-players, with a mean difference of 5.85 points ($t(329.63) = 3.48, p = 0.0006$), suggesting potential cognitive enhancement related to gameplay (MOPA) An experimental study conducted by Jordan and Dhamala in 2022 on 47 participants, 28 Video Game Players (VGP) and 19 Non-Video Game Players (NVGP) using fMRI showed that VGP exhibited enhanced reasoning task performance. Another meta-analysis study conducted by Bediou in 2018 used 89 studies and showed that video games enhanced cognitive functions depending on gameplay demands, such as visual attention and cognitive flexibility. Previous studies in this area have shown that exposure to the highly dynamic environments of Multiplayer Online Battle Arena (MOBA) games can enhance specific cognitive functions, such as reasoning and attentional control (Bediou et al., 2018; Jordan & Dhamala, 2022).

However, the present study found no significant association between memory functions and video game playing ($t(335.15) = 1.38, p = 0.1692$). Similarly, Dixon in 2020 conducted a study at Pacific Union College examining the effects of video games on short-term and long-term memory. His study involved 42 participants divided into two groups: gamers and non-gamers. The findings showed that video game players outperform non-video game players in short-term memory tasks. However, no significant difference was found between the two groups in long-term memory performance.

The one-way ANOVA results shown in (Table 3) revealed no statistically significant difference in cognitive scores based on the duration of video game play (in years). This finding suggested that the length of gaming experience did not significantly affect cognitive functions.

Similarly, as shown in Table 4, the Kruskal-Wallis test indicated no statistically significant differences in total cognitive function scores based on daily gaming Time, measured by hours per day ($\chi^2(4) = 3.97, p = 0.141$). Thus, the number of hours spent gaming daily did not significantly influence cognitive functions among participants.

A study done by Jadallah in 2022 investigated the association between video game play and cognitive function among 160 students: 78 boys and 82 girls, using a standardized assessment instrument (CogAT). They found no significant association between playtime or video game type and cognitive test scores. Similarly, the current study did not find a significant association between the improvement of cognitive functions and the amount of time spent playing video games, as shown in Table 4. This suggested that video game engagement alone did not predict cognitive test performance. (Jadallah et al., 2022)

On the other hand, Previous research by Green and Bavelier in 2003 examined the impact of action video games on visual attention among young adults aged between 18 and 23 years (VGPs) and non-video game players (NVGPs). For at least one hour per day, four days per week, over the past six months. The findings show that action video game players outperformed non-video game players across various visual attention tasks.

Similarly, another research study by (Latham, et al., 2013) showed that both brief and extensive video game experiences were associated with enhancements in cognitive functions. However, they emphasized the need for further research to explore the underlying mechanisms and better understand how video game play might lead to such a broad range of cognitive improvements. Many studies highlighted that participants defined as "expert gamers" based on limited playtime, which may be a few hours per week over six months. Furthermore, there is no standardized or objective measure of video game proficiency across different genres (Greenfield et al. 1994)

Regarding Table 5, the results showed no significant association between participants' perceptions of the cognitive benefits of video games and their actual cognitive performance levels, as showed by the Chi-square test ($p = 0.9889$). This suggested that positive perceptions regarding the cognitive benefits of gaming were common across different levels of performance. In contrast, AlWhaibi in 2024 examined the impact of video games on self-reported spatial abilities using a survey conducted among 566 university students. Participants who reported frequent gaming also reported higher spatial abilities compared to those who played less frequently. However, despite these self-reports, no measurable cognitive enhancements were found, suggesting that individuals may overestimate the cognitive benefits of gaming. These findings align with the current study.

As shown in Table 6 multiple linear regression was computed predicting the total score of cognitive functions based on college type and playing video games. The regression equation was significant ($F = 10.9966, p < 0.0001$). These findings are consistent with those reported by Mahmoud et al in 2022 who examined the relationship between video game usage and cognitive functions among adolescents. The study was conducted on students from two faculties, Nursing, and Art at Zagazig University, using a convenience sampling technique, among 384 participants. The results show a significant association between cognitive function levels and faculty type, with approximately half of the nursing students demonstrating higher levels of cognitive functions compared to art students. This outcome may be attributed to the nature of the academic content in scientific disciplines, such as nursing, which requires greater concentration and cognitive effort for comprehension, as it involves higher order thinking skills and mental abilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, video games may have a positive impact when used in moderation, as they contribute to the development of certain cognitive functions such as attention, coordination, reasoning, perception, and information processing. The comparison between video game players and non-players revealed significant differences in total cognitive function scores. Specifically, video game players demonstrated notable improvements in cognitive domains. However, the findings indicated that video game playing did not have a significant impact on memory performance. Also, there are no statistically significant differences in total cognitive function scores across Daily Video Game Play Time and no statistically significant difference in the cognitive scores across the groups based on the number of years participants have been playing video games. Overall, these results suggest that video games can offer several cognitive benefits. Nevertheless, it remains important to approach gaming in a balanced and mindful manner to mitigate potential negative effects.

Recommendations

Despite the existing improvement and the positive results of this research from the improvement of some cognitive functions such as attention, coordination, reasoning, and Perception. We would like to emphasize that we do not support excessive and addictive play, as the use should be moderate and balanced. We recommend future research by developing programs aimed at teaching individuals how to achieve a healthy balance between benefiting from play and not entering the negative area. We also recommend research to study the long-term impact of MOBA games, and the impact of group play on social skills.

Limitations

Certain limitations should be considered when interpreting the results of this study. For starters, because the study is cross-sectional, the data cannot be used to infer causality and temporality. Second, the study utilized a GCFA task with a duration of 30 to 40 minutes, which is quite lengthy. Moreover, the findings are specific to PNU students in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, and may not be generalizable to students at other universities. It should also be noted that PNU is an all-female university, meaning the entire sample consisted of female students. Despite these limitations, this study is among the first to examine the impact of MOBA on certain cognitive functions in PNU students.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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